

The JAFFE Dataset as a Polemical Straw Man in *How to See Like a Machine*

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Abstract

Trevor Paglen’s forthcoming book *How to See Like a Machine* (Paglen, 2026) reprises, in simplified form, a critique of the JAFFE dataset first advanced with Kate Crawford in “Excavating AI” (Crawford & Paglen, 2021). The new version is shorter, harsher, and more categorical. It presents JAFFE as though it embodied a crude ontology of emotion, while omitting published rebuttals to the earlier critique. This note argues that the book mischaracterizes JAFFE by inflating a limited operational framework into a sweeping claim about “inner emotional states.” It further places that dispute in a documented context of prior objections, published replies, public accusation, and private hostility. Criticism of datasets is legitimate and necessary, but it should itself meet standards of accuracy, context, and documentary fairness.

Keywords: JAFFE, dataset criticism, mischaracterization, omission, documentary fairness

Introduction

Trevor Paglen’s forthcoming book *How to See Like a Machine* (Paglen, 2026) returns to the critique of the JAFFE dataset in a form that is more compressed, harsher in tone, and more categorical than the earlier treatment published with Kate Crawford in “Excavating AI.” The new account presents JAFFE as though it embodied a simplistic ontology of emotion. It portrays the dataset’s assumptions as “absurd” and frames JAFFE as a paradigmatic example of the distortions it attributes to machine-learning datasets. That framing is misleading.

How to Misread JAFFE

The Japanese Female Facial Expression (JAFFE) dataset (Lyons, Kamachi, & Gyoba, 1997) was created in the 1990s as a constrained research resource for work on facial expression perception, not as a training set for machine-learning systems and not as a grand claim about emotional interiority. Its images are posed facial expressions, and these are accompanied by multidimensional semantic ratings on several expression terms by observers. To criticize the use of such material is legitimate. To frame the dataset as though its creators had asserted a simplistic theory of interior emotional truth is not. A central characteristic of Paglen’s new treatment is inflation. A limited operational framework is turned into a grand ontological claim. A dataset built from photographs of posed facial expressions taken under controlled laboratory conditions is rhetorically transformed into an assertion that emotions are fixed, visually transparent natural kinds, uniformly measurable across a population. That move may be polemically expedient, but it does not faithfully represent JAFFE’s documentation or the purposes for which the images were created.

Context and Documentation of the Dispute

Readers encountering JAFFE through Paglen's new book are likely to come away with a misleading caricature of the dataset and of its creators' intentions. Importantly, the relevant objections have already been made public. Detailed rebuttals to the treatment of JAFFE in "Excavating AI" were published, showing where that account was inaccurate and dependent on straw-man portrayals of the dataset's assumptions (Lyons, 2020; Lyons, 2021a). Yet Paglen's book passage appears to escalate the earlier critique rather than acknowledge or engage with those rebuttals.

This dispute over JAFFE has not been merely theoretical. In September 2021, after I objected to his posting of JAFFE images on Twitter, Trevor Paglen replied by email: "This is fair use. Please fuck off." (Lyons, 2021b). Shortly thereafter, he publicly accused me on Twitter of harassment and other misconduct, while tagging my employer. Because I had been blocked from replying on the same platform, I published a brief note to document and answer those accusations (Lyons, 2021c). These public and private exchanges demonstrate that the present issue is not simply one of scholarly disagreement over dataset politics. It is also a case in which a disputed interpretation has been repeatedly amplified while prior objections and rebuttals have not been acknowledged.

Conclusion

A fair critique of JAFFE would acknowledge that expression datasets rely on operational assumptions, that such assumptions can later be reified by users, and that categories of facial expression deserve scrutiny. These are serious points for discussion. But it would also acknowledge the limits of what JAFFE claimed, the context in which it was created, and the existence of published rebuttals to earlier mischaracterizations. Without that, the new account reads not as careful correction but as repeated indictment that declines engagement with prior refutation. Criticism of datasets should itself meet the standards of accuracy, context, and documentary fairness that it demands of others. When a disputed example is reissued in harsher form while contrary evidence and prior rebuttals are omitted, the result is not clarification but further distortion.

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